

THE DEVELOPMENT OF MEDICINE IN THE ANCIENT WESTERN COUNTRIES, AND THE CONTRIBUTION OF ALLOMAS TO THE DEVELOPMENT.

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Annotation: *The importance of general medicine in the life of the organism, the interrelated aspects of the organism, the great role of great scientists in medicine, as well as the specificity of the medicine of the ancient Western countries and their medicine, as well as the study of the significant innovations that have taken place in them, while knowing the main branches of development in medicine in Western countries. The main purpose of the article is to study the medicine of the ancient West. In addition, the development of medicine and the contribution of our great scientists to this development were partially described, albeit briefly, based on the latest developments in modern Western medicine.*

Keywords: *Surgeon, therapist, panacea, prescription, hospital, anatomy, hospital.*

Introduction. Ancient Greece (Greece) was one of the most highly developed countries in science and culture on the European continent. Legends and poems about ancient Greek medicine have come down to us in the form of a number of cultural treasures. In ancient Greece, Apollo was worshiped in all fields, including medicine. The first source for us to study the history of ancient Greek medicine is Homer's Iliad. The play details the battle of the Greeks on the threshold of Troy. Homer points out that doctors from the Greek army also took part in the war. Homer wrote that doctors treated the wounded and sick soldiers, removed bullets from their bodies and bandaged their wounds. According to the author, it is

possible to find out the level of development of Greek medicine at that time. It is said that the Trojan War took place in the 12th century BC (1193-1184). This means that the Greeks had military medicine in the 12th century BC. An important legend is associated with Homer's Iliad. The poem states that Asclepius, a physician later known as the "god of medicine," took part in the Trojan War. He had two sons, Mahaon and Podaliri, and two daughters, Higieya and Panakeya. They were also doctors and involved in the treatment of Greek soldiers. Maxaon underwent surgery. Podaliri was a therapist.

Panakea, on the other hand, knew how to make medicine for any ailment. They called this medicine panacea. There really can't be a drug like that. The word panacea is now used figuratively. No information about Maxaon. As for Podaliri, legends say that all his future generations were also engaged in medical work.

There is another aspect of the legend of Asclepius. Legend has it that Asclepius was not born of his mother. He was taken out by his father Apollo (sun god) and his mother Cronida by cutting her abdomen (by caesarean section). This legend shows that the method of cesarean section was known in ancient Greek medicine as early as the 12th century BC. . This means that surgery and women's treatment were very advanced at that time. In ancient Greece, doctors were highly valued. For example, Homer writes, "One experienced doctor is better than ten others."

The main source for the study of ancient Greek medicine is a book called the Hippocratic Collection. This book was written in the V-IV centuries BC. The book is named after the famous Greek physician Hippocrates (Hippocrates) because the book was started by Hippocrates and continued by his disciples. The book is mainly about applied medicine.

In Greece, medicine developed in two directions. The first is the formation and development of the medical profession, and the second is the emergence of church medicine. In the history of Greek medicine, church medicine did not play a significant role.

Applied medicine, on the other hand, is well developed and has made significant strides. The advanced teachings of the great Greek philosophers (Democritus, Anaximenes) played an important role in this. Democritus's atomistic theory deserves special mention here. This theory has been of great help in understanding the nature (structure and properties) of the human body. The development of applied medicine was as follows: small doctors first established small and then larger hospitals to treat patients in their homes. They are called 'yatreyya'. Experienced doctors have also opened a medical school at the hospital.

In such a school, the teachers were called 'yatrolipt', i.e. medical teachers. At the end of the study period, the students took an exam and swore to serve with integrity.

Gerofil did not have a clear idea about the causes of the disease. He also acknowledged that the disease was caused by divine forces. However, in the treatment of some diseases, in addition to reading various spells, he also used drugs.

According to Gerophilus, each disease has its own medicine, and the doctor's job is to take it and use it. He used many recipes in practical medicine. The development of anatomy and physiology is associated with the name of another Alexandrian scientist. Erazistrat himself was from Asia Minor. He lived in the III century BC. Date of birth unknown, year of death 280 years. Erazistrat was well versed in medical science at that time and successfully treated diseases. Erazistratus reportedly began his medical career by studying human anatomy and made important discoveries in this field. For example, he was one of the first to know that the brain is covered with soft and hard membranes, that the brain is composed of curved pits, and that there are fluid-retaining ventricles in the brain. Another important discovery of Erasistratus was that he was one of the first to discover that the brain has motor and sensory nerves. In doing so, he proved that the movement of the organs is controlled by the brain. It was a great discovery for medicine at that time. Erazistrat examined the heart and blood vessels both anatomically and physiologically. He saw them move. He found that there was a heart and a corridor of the heart. He examined the organs in the abdomen and examined the peristalsis of the intestine. He thought that food was mechanically processed in the intestines because of peristalsis. This idea has been confirmed in recent studies.

The works of Claudius Galen, a famous medical scientist, and other great judges of that time are the main sources for studying the history of ancient Roman medicine. These works provide information about Western European medicine at that time and its achievements.

ASKLEPIAD

Asclepiad (131-5 BC) was originally Greek. He was educated in Athens and Alexandria and became a famous judge. He moved to Rome in 95 BC and lived there for the rest of his life. Asclepiad, like Hippocrates, is based on an atomistic theory of human nature. He calls atoms particles. According to the scientist, these invisible tiny particles are constantly moving through the very thin tubes present

in the body. If for some reason there is an obstruction in the path of these particles, this place will change and disease will occur.

In matters of treatment, Asclepiad recommends the following principle: The patient should be treated in a reliable, rapid, and painless manner. He rarely used surgical techniques that hurt the patient. But he was a good surgeon. He was one of the first to develop a tracheotomy. He recommended methods of treating the patient from natural factors, such as fresh air, massage. He also made extensive use of physical exercise.

Cornelius Sel's main service was that he collected and organized the works of all the famous physicians who had gone before him, enriched them with his own experiences, and published them as a separate book. Cornelius Sel's wrote a 70-volume work called *Artes* (Art). Volume 8 (Volumes VI-XIII) of this work is devoted to medicine and is called "On Medicine".

This book describes the basic principles and practical tasks of medicine, in particular, surgical diseases and their treatment.

It is no coincidence that Sel's included this work in his book "Art". Scientists of the past considered medicine to be an art. The great Hippocrates said, "Medicine is the greatest art." It is a great art to diagnose and treat people. As with any art, medicine requires a certain amount of talent and ability. Not everyone with a medical degree is a professional. In addition to knowledge, medicine requires skill and ability. So it is true that medicine is an art.

In ancient Rome, there were specialized medical schools where doctors were trained. In addition to medical knowledge, they taught grammar, history, literature, rhetoric, mathematics, astronomy, and philosophy. The most famous of the ancient Roman physicians is Galen.

KLAVDIY GALEN

One of the most famous physicians of the ancient world was Claudius Galen. He became famous as the greatest scientist and physician in the history of world medicine after Hippocrates. He was known in his time as a great theorist, scientist, anatomist, experimenter, and physician. Galen has left a big mark on the history of world medicine.

Claudius Galen was born in 131 in Pergamum. His father, Nikon, was a famous architect. He was a very wealthy man, so he was able to educate his son Claudius.

Galen, with his deep knowledge and good practical experience, successfully treated sick and wounded gladiators. As a result, he gained great fame. In 164, Galen was invited to Rome, to the palace of Emperor Marcus Aurelius, and was

appointed emperor's court physician. After the death of Mark Aurelius, Galen became the personal physician of his son Commodus. It took a long time to become a palace doctor. But Galen not only cured the emperor, his family and palace officials from diseases, but in his spare time he read books and conducted various experiments. In particular, he conducted anatomical and physiological examinations. In the field of anatomy, Galen made many discoveries. For example, he found that the walls of organs (stomach, uterus, blood vessels) consist of several layers, not one. Galen had a deep heart and vascular work. Galen greatly enriched the science of anatomy and physiology. For example, by examining the process of breathing, he found that the chest muscles and the diaphragm were involved. They have been shown to expand the chest and help with breathing. One of Galen's greatest contributions was that he was the first to introduce experimental methods in medicine. He experimentally identified the basic functions of the human brain. In medicine, the idea was that the human brain was as large a gland as any other gland in the body. Galen proved this idea wrong.

The brain has proven to be the center of movement, thinking, intuition, and mental activity. The famous philosopher Aristotle, on the other hand, was of the opinion that the heart is the center of human perception and thought. Galen found 7 pairs of nerve endings and a stray nerve coming out of the brain. By cutting through all parts of the animal's spinal cord, it examined the loss of movement and sensory function, and proved that the brain is indeed the center of motion and sensation. Galen demonstrated the movement of blood vessels in the body with his experimental methods. But he made a mistake. He thought that the center of the circulatory system was the liver. According to him, the ingested food turns into blood in the liver, enters the veins, and travels through the veins to the organs, where it is absorbed and destroyed. Galen thought that there was an open path between the right ventricle and the left ventricle of the heart, through which blood flows from the right ventricle to the left ventricle.

Galen was based on the humoral theory of the origin of disease, according to the understanding of the time. He understood that the various fluids in the human body determine both health and disease. According to Galen, any disease goes through four stages: the onset of the disease, its progression, the period of full development, and the period of decline. While this concept is true for some infectious diseases, it is not true for all diseases.

Hippocrates once wrote that there are ready-made medicines in nature. Galen disagrees. According to him, medicinal plants in nature also contain unnecessary substances. Galen teaches that it is the pharmacologist's job to separate the drug

from these excess substances. He also determined the proportionality of the amount and volume of drugs. Galen has also written several works on etiology and pathogenesis. In the matter of therapy, Galen also stood by the principle that the opposite should be treated with the opposite. At the same time, it emphasizes the need to use the body's own internal forces. Galen paid special attention to diet therapy. According to him, many diseases can be treated through diet. He also highlighted the role of exercise in disease prevention. Galen can be called the founder of Gerontology. He studied in depth the changes that take place in the bodies and organs of the elderly. According to Galen, in old age, the body's natural biological state changes and the body becomes like a dead tree. Older people have decreased appetite, fatigue, poor digestion, and limited mobility. There are also diseases of the elderly. For example, various arthritis and osteoarthritis, gout, asthma, paresis and paralysis, bone, spinal deformity, etc. To maintain the health of the elderly, Galen advises that first of all it is necessary to regulate the diet, gradually engage in physical activity, to avoid disorders of the gastrointestinal tract. Recommended special hygienic measures for the elderly.

Galen was a very talented scientist. He has written more than 400 works in many fields of science. Many of these are devoted to various fields of medicine. They, in particular, describe all the theoretical and practical areas of medicine. As an encyclopedic scholar, Galen also wrote works on philosophy, mathematics, grammar, and logic. However, he paid more attention to medicine. Galen has covered important topics in his medical field. In particular, he provided accurate information on anatomy, physiology, internal medicine, hygiene, surgery, and gynecology.

Among Galen's most important works on medicine are: "Anatomical Investigations", "The Importance of Human Body Parts", "The Art of Medicine", "Methods of Treatment", "On Sick Organs", "On the Composition of Medicines", "Hygiene", "Hippocratic Rules" and so on. Many of Galen's works were burned at the stake in Rome. Only about a hundred of his medical works have survived. In The Art of Medicine and The Methods of Treatment, Galen expressed his views on the importance of medicine and its functions. One of Galen's greatest works on medicine is his book, The Importance of Parts of the Human Body. The book consists of 17 volumes and discusses the structure of the human body, its properties and the functions of its organs. In medieval medicine, Galen's books were taught as textbooks. Even now, some of Galen's works have not lost their value. Galen died in Rome in 201, at the age of 70.

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